

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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SIMULATED EDUCATION AND MODERN MEDICINE

Aminova Mohinur Normurod qizi

Student of the Faculty of Medicine, Tashkent Medical Academy, Termiz Branch
No. 1

aminovamohinur133@gmail.com

Abstract: Today, the most important urgent issue is to carry out active and useful work in the field of human health care, to improve the medical culture of our people. By strengthening both material and spiritual attention to medical science, by implementing the results of fundamental and scientific and innovative researches, the rise of medical culture in the society is achieved. As a result, this has a positive effect on the development of modern national medicine. It is known that medical culture is a solid foundation of the future of society. In this regard, first of all, young people should understand the need to have a medical culture and approach it with determination, self-confidence and responsibility, pay serious attention to the acquisition of medical knowledge, become more familiar with the theory and practice of medical activity, it is necessary to be able to connect knowledge with life and practice.

Key words: Medical education, student, educational institution, medicine, simulation education, national program.

A new approach, a new methodology, and a new professional skill are required from a teacher who is in line with the requirements of the present time, who has mastered the latest achievements of science and technology, and who can apply our national and spiritual values to the educational system. . For many years, the educational process in the system of general and professional education was built on a deductive basis in accordance with the didactic trinity "knowledge - skill - competence". it was considered that it can be absorbed. And the process of forming skills requires long and many repetitions. Therefore, an important aspect of the teacher's work in the process of forming a unique skill for a student is to constantly monitor the educational process, make the necessary corrections for the correct formation of the skill, ensure that mistakes are not repeated during repeated repetition, and most importantly, it is important to determine that errors are not

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detected. Therefore, in this sense, special attention is now being paid instead of simulation education. imitation using an artificial (mechanical or computer) system. Currently, there are seven groups of simulation technologies for medical education, according to the level of realism.

The simulation method has been shown to effectively improve medical knowledge, procedural skills, ease of performing taught tasks, interprofessional communication, teamwork, and teaching skills. It's important to have a common mental model of what we mean by simulation, which David Gaba defines as "a technique, rather than a technology, of replacing or augmenting real experience with controlled experiences that fully evoke or reproduce important aspects of the real world in an interactive way." riffs. It provides a safe environment in which confidence and competence can be consistently achieved as a goal of patient care.

The difference between medical education and other types of education is that not only theoretical knowledge but also doctor's experience and practical skills are imparted to students. Professional skills and abilities are not transferred "from hand to hand" by the teacher to the student along with knowledge. These skills are formed as a result of the student's independent activities organized by experienced teachers. In medical universities, we must create such an environment in which the student's needs for self-improvement and learning must be developed. Because medical education does not end after graduation, but continues "for a lifetime". The task of a pedagogue of a medical university is to clearly organize and effectively manage the independent activities of students, that is, to set tasks, correct the ways to solve them, record and evaluate the results of student efforts. If a student does not learn to learn independently, then he will not become a good doctor who can correctly analyze his work and make a critical observation. But today, despite all our efforts, graduates of medical universities do not have practical skills to work on high-tech, innovative equipment. Often their knowledge is limited only to theory. Only a number of young doctors can improve their skills in foreign clinics or educational institutions, because their costs are quite high. Doctors must constantly apply the acquired skills. Traditional forms of medical education do not provide a completely safe and effective training before the doctor is actively working with patients. In addition, the current forms of monitoring the level of competence of doctors are inconsistent or insufficient.

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In the department of simulation training, practical training in internal medicine for students of the 3rd-5th year is carried out on the basis of simulation training. Simulation techniques and technologies, algorithms and standards, simulators and phantoms help students learn skills and acquire practical skills in the form of automaticity. In the process of simulation, it is possible to create a pre-learning environment that allows the use of existing clinical devices and consumables in "real" conditions, in real time. Unlike the usual conditions of the classroom, simulators allow the student to experience extreme situations, o It allows to think independently and actively, not to memorize information passively. In the 1st stage of training, students of 3-4 years repeat and improve the methods of examining patients in normal and pathological conditions by organs and systems (palpation of lungs and heart, percussion, auscultation, measurement of AB). Students will also have the opportunity to learn the skills of recording an EKG and analyzing changes. At this stage of training, students' acquired practical skills are monitored through test control. In the 2nd stage of training, 5th-year students learn to make a diagnosis and provide practical assistance in urgent cases adapted to real situations based on the "Patient came to the doctor" training.

Conclusion: The correct organization of the practice process using simulation technologies provides an opportunity to acquire professional practical skills at a higher level than the theoretical description and is one of the effective teaching methods for the formation of students' professional skills.

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